

Studies on Biologically Active Heterocycles. Part-VI. Synthesis and Biological Activity of 3,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones and Thiophosphate Derivatives

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1,3,4-Oxadiazol-2-thiones show a broad spectrum of biological activities¹⁻³. Organophosphates are widely used for controlling pests^{4,7}.

In continuation of our interest in the chemistry of heterocycles⁸, the benzoyl derivatives (3a-n) and diethylthiophosphates (4a-g), of 3-alkyl/aryl/aralkylaminomethyl-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (3a-n) were synthesised with a view to getting more active insecticides and bactericides. The 5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (1) was prepared⁸ from 2,4-dichlorobenzoylhydrazine. Compounds 2a-n were prepared⁴ by the reaction of thione (1), formaldehyde (35%) and appropriate alkyl/aryl amines in ethanol. The benzoyl derivatives (3a-n) were synthesised by benzylation of 2. The thiophosphates (4a-g) were prepared⁶ by the action of *O,O*-diethylthiophosphoryl chloride on 2 in

presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone (Scheme 1). All the compounds gave satisfactory spectral data (Table 1).

The benzoyl derivatives (3a-n) were screened for their antibacterial activities using agar-plate diffusion technique⁹. For screening, 24 h-old culture of *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus megatarium* QMB 1552 were used as test organisms. The results show that compound 3 was found to be very active against all the organisms whereas 4c, e, f, i and l moderately active.

The thiophosphate derivatives (4a-g) were screened for insecticidal activity against *Drosophila melanogaster*-Maigen by residual film evaporation method¹⁰. The activities were evaluated using solution of the compounds (0.01-0.00001%) in acetone and does dependence studies were carried

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-n AND 4a-g

Compd. no.	R'	Yield (%)	M.p. °C	δ
3a	C ₆ H ₅	70	140	5.0 (2H, s), 6.6-8.0 (m, 8 ArH)
b	2-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	78	117	3.4 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.4-7.6 (m, 7 ArH)
c	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	79	171	5.2 (2H, s), 6.3-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
d	3-Cl C ₆ H ₄	76	168	5.0 (2H, s), 6.6-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
e	4-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	74	131	3.5 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.4-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
f	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70	162	1.7 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.4-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
g	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	79	170	1.9 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.5-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
h	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	68	175	4.0 (2H, s), 5.0 (2H, s), 6.8-7.7 (m, 8 ArH)
i	4-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	72	194	5.1 (2H, s), 6.8-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
j	2-Cl C ₆ H ₄	78	198	5.6 (2H, s), 7.0-8.1 (m, 7 ArH)
k	3-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	74	145	5.3 (2H, s), 6.7-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
l	2-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	68	185	5.3 (2H, s), 7.4-8.1 (m, 7 ArH)
m	2,4-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	81	133	4.6 (2H, s), 6.9-7.7 (m, 6 ArH)
n	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	65	138	0.7 (3H, t, J 7Hz), 1.4 (2H, q, J 7Hz), 2.8 (2H, q, J 7Hz), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.8-7.7 (m, 3 ArH)
4a	C ₆ H ₅	45	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.8-7.8 (m, 8 ArH)
b	2-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	40	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.4 (2H, s), 6.9-7.9 (m, 7 ArH)
c	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	48	Gummy	1.4 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.4 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.3 (2H, s), 6.6-8.1 (m, 7 ArH)
d	3-Cl C ₆ H ₄	49	Gummy	1.4 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.6 (2H, s), 6.9-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
e	4-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	45	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.4 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.4 (2H, s), 6.8-7.6 (m, 7 ArH)
f	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	48	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.4 (2H, s), 6.9-7.9 (m, 7 ArH)
g	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	42	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.5 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.9-7.9 (m, 7 ArH)